

NOAA Estuary-of-the-Month
Seminar Series No. 14

Lake Erie Estuarine Systems: Issues, Resources, Status, and Management

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Lake Erie Estuarine Systems: Issues, Resources, Status, and Management

Proceedings of a Seminar
Held May 4, 1988
Washington, D.C.

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
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National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
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NOAA Estuarine Programs Office
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LAKE ERIE AND ITS ESTUARINE SYSTEMS

(Issues, Resources, Status, and Management)

an
**ESTUARY-OF-THE-MONTH
SEMINAR**

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at the
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**THE NOAA ESTUARINE PROGRAMS OFFICE
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edited
by
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PREFACE

This volume contains the proceedings of a one-day seminar on Lake Erie with emphasis on its nearshore and coastal wetland areas. The presentations were made on 4 May 1988 at the Herbert C. Hoover Building of the U.S. Department of Commerce in Washington, D.C., as part of a series of "Estuary-of-the-Month" seminars sponsored by the NOAA Estuarine Programs Office (EPO). The objectives of this series are to bring to public attention the important research and management issues regarding our nation's estuaries.

The Laurentian Great Lakes of North America represent our nation's "sweetwater seas" and its "fourth coast." The National Sea Grant College Program administered by NOAA includes active research, education and extension programs in most of the Great Lakes States. Furthermore, the southern shore of Lake Erie in Ohio is the site of the only freshwater National Estuarine Research Reserve. Therefore, it was appropriate that the Estuary-of-the-Month seminar series would include Lake Erie.

The present seminar was originally arranged and organized by Dr. C. E. "Eddie" Herdendorf, recent director of the Ohio Sea Grant Program as well as director of The Ohio State University's Center for Lake Erie Area Research (CLEAR) and its Franz Theodore Stone Laboratory on South Bass Island in Lake Erie. In view of his ensuing retirement, Dr. Herdendorf asked me to assume the roles of coordinator and moderator of the seminar and editor of the proceedings.

The title of this volume undoubtedly raises some eyebrows. Indeed, researchers actively debate the use of the terms "estuary" and "estuarine" to describe certain estuarine-like physical processes characteristic of many of Lake Erie's wetlands and its flooded tributary mouths. Contrasting views on the appropriate terminology are found in several of the presentations. Thus, it is important, in order to understand the estuarine-like characteristics of these areas, that these proceedings present first the geological and physical nature of Lake Erie and its coastal regions. The succeeding papers summarize the chemistry and biology of the nearshore and coastal areas, both within the historical context and the context of present conditions of pollution and physical modification. Of great importance to the future condition of the Lake Erie ecosystem are the views and policies of government, throughout the local, state or provincial, and national hierarchy as well as at the binational level. These issues are succinctly covered by representatives of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's Great Lakes National Program Office, and Environment Canada's Inland Waters Directorate.

The seminar originated through discussions in 1987 between Dr. Herdendorf and Dr. James Thomas, then of the Estuarine Programs Office, followed by later coordination with Dr. Carl Berman and Dr. Joe Bishop of the EPO, as well as with Dr. Virginia Tippie, EPO Director. Special appreciation is extended to Ms. Terri Weininger for retyping several of the manuscripts, and to Ms. Nancy Creamer for editorial assistance, both at Heidelberg College. The Ohio Sea Grant College Program supported travel costs for two of the participants under federal grant number NA84AA-D-00079, the National Sea Grant College Program, NOAA, U.S. Department of Commerce. Dr. David B. Baker, Director of the Water Quality Laboratory at Heidelberg College, generously provided the use of computers, supplies, secretarial assistance, and some of my time for coordination and editorial efforts.

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OVERVIEW OF LAKE ERIE AND ITS ESTUARIES WITHIN THE GREAT LAKES ECOSYSTEM

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INTRODUCTION

The St. Lawrence Great Lakes of North America comprise about 20% of the world's supply of surface freshwater. This concentration is rivaled only by Lake Baikal in Siberia and the rift valley great lakes of east Africa. Taken together these three loci account for over 60% of the water in the earth's freshwater lakes (Herdendorf 1982). Like the oceans, large lakes can possess estuarine-like environments in the lower reaches of tributary streams. These types of environments are particularly prevalent in our Great Lakes where crustal rebound, following deglaciation, has caused the northern portion of the basin to rise over 100 m. As a result, the lower courses of the southern tributaries have been flooded, creating the drowned river mouths typical of estuarine systems. The following overview will discuss the natural setting of the Great Lakes with particular focus on Lake Erie, the most southerly of the Great Lakes and thus the one exhibiting the best developed estuaries. This discussion will be followed by a review of the cultural setting of the Great Lakes region, the impact human settlement has had on the ecosystem, and attempts to manage our delicate freshwater estuaries.

The North American Great Lakes system within the United States extends from Duluth, Minnesota, at the western end of Lake Superior, to Massena, New York on the St. Lawrence River (Fig 1). It possesses a shoreline length of over 6,000 km and a water surface area of 158,000 km². The Great Lakes are located within the highly industrialized northcentral United States. The Great Lakes drainage basin covers only 4% of the United States land area, but it has 15% of the nation's population and produces 50% of the nation's steel. The basin consists of land and water areas of 183 counties in eight states. The coastal resources of the Great Lakes, including their estuaries and wetlands, are invaluable assets to the region and to the nation as a whole. The need to wisely develop these resources within the context of sound environmental practices is a continuing challenge for resources managers.

Figure 1. St. Lawrence Great Lakes.

NATURAL SETTING OF THE GREAT LAKES BASIN

Morphometry of the Great Lakes

The five Great Lakes range in surface area from 82,100 km² (Lake Superior) to 18,960 km² (Lake Ontario) and in volume from 12,100 km³ (Lake Superior) to 484 km³ (Lake Erie). Morphometric dimensions of the Great Lakes and their connecting waterways are listed in Tables 1 through 4. The relative depths, surface elevations, and water storage capacities of the five Great Lakes are graphically shown on Fig. 2.

Rawson (1939) was among the first limnologists to articulate the interactions of the major physical and chemical factors which control the productivity of a lake. Fig. 3 shows his attempt to organize the physical and chemical factors in the metabolism of a lake. This organization has stood the test of time and provides us with a useful conceptual model for developing a classification and inventory of aquatic habitats. Rawson (1955) further demonstrated that in large lakes, morphometry is a dominant factor in productivity. There is a tendency for standing crop per unit area to decrease with an increase in maximum depth. Wetzel (1983) points out that the morphology of a lake basin is best described by a detailed bathymetric map (Fig. 4) and that such a map is essential for the evaluation of the effects that morphology has on nearly all of the physical, chemical, and biological processes of a lake. Useful morphometric information contained on a bathymetric map includes: (1) area, (2) mean and maximum depth, (3) volume, (4) fetch length, (5) shoreline length, (6) basin slope, and (7) orientation (Hutchinson 1957). Rawson also showed the factors influencing lake productivity could be grouped into three categories: (1) edaphic, e.g., total dissolved solids, nutrients, (2) morphometric, e.g., mean depth, lake surface area, and (3) climatic, e.g., air temperature, latitude. He demonstrated that given adequate information, on these factors, a multiple correlation analysis would show a direct relationship to fish production.

Thus, lake morphometry has a profound influence on the quality and quantity of important fish and wildlife habitat. Those habitats that are most critical are often near the coast and subject to human perturbation. Each Great Lake can be divided into two zones: (1) an offshore pelagic zone, characterized by fine-grained sediment types, great depths, and a generally less diverse habitat than nearshore and (2) a nearshore zone which contains important spawning and nursery habitat for fish. This zone is the receptacle for nutrients, contaminants, and sediments from the surrounding watershed, and is prone to development, with its accompanying water intakes, rip-rapped harbors and shorelines, power plants, sewage treatment plants, industrial outfalls, and wetlands destruction. Basin morphometry is a confining factor for fish since it sets the limits within which species can reproduce, feed, and compete. In the Great Lakes, some species of fish spawn every month of the year and each species has specific spawning requirements. The open water pelagic zone is used by such species as bloaters and deepwater sculpin. The nearshore

Figure 2. Morphometric relationship of the Great Lakes.

Figure 3. Factors influencing the biological productivity of a lake (after Rawson 1939)

Figure 4. Lake Erie bathymetry (m).

pelagic zone is used by alewife, rainbow smelt, yellow perch, white bass, and gizzard shad, while the nearshore benthic environment is used by slimy sculpin, trout-perch, and johnny darters to cite a few examples (Jude et al. 1979). Connecting rivers, lakes, and estuarine marshes such as Saginaw Bay, Sandusky Bay, and Green Bay, are also important spawning and nursery areas for such species as white suckers, carp, emerald shiners, yellow perch, walleye, and northern pike. Thus, the quantity and quality of these habitat types are critical elements affecting the final species composition in each of the Great Lakes.

A total of 1,370 coastal wetlands fringe the Great Lakes and their connecting channels, for a combined wetland area of 1,209 km² (Table 5). The greatest number and area of coastal wetlands ring Lake Michigan, the only Great Lake entirely within the United States. Lake Superior has the second highest number of wetlands, but they are relatively small in size. On the average, the largest wetlands are found along Lake Huron and its discharge channel to the south, particularly the delta wetland of the St. Clair River which covers 35 km². The highly industrialized Lake Erie shore has the smallest number and area of wetlands while Lake Ontario has the smallest average size of wetlands, largely due to isolated marshes in the Thousand Islands area of the St. Lawrence River. The presence or absence of estuaries and coastal wetlands is largely dictated by the geomorphology of a given shoreline and the recent history of water level fluctuations. Each lake has a particular set of geomorphic features which exert control on wetland development (see Paleogeography and Geomorphology chapter).

Hydrology of the Great Lakes

By oceanic standards the Great Lakes are small, having a total area of 244,000 km² or about 0.25% of the world ocean. But as we have seen, by lake standards they are large. However, the relative dimensions of the Great Lakes and the oceans are remarkably similar. For example, comparison of the largest and deepest ocean, the Pacific, with the largest and deepest Great Lake, Superior, reveals that both are about 4,000 times as wide as their mean depths, and 1,500 times as wide as their maximum depths (Ragotzkie 1983). As in the oceans, the circulation of the Great Lakes is primarily wind-driven. Currents in the Great Lakes tend to be parallel to the coasts. Ekman transport and the resulting coastal upwelling or downwelling leads to strong horizontal temperature gradients normal to the coast. The overall circulation pattern takes the form of gyres, either encompassing an entire lake as frequently occurs in Lake Ontario or as several gyres as in Lake Michigan and Lake Superior (Ragotzkie 1983).

The tides of the ocean also have their analogy in the wind-driven seiches of the Great Lakes. These surface oscillations which are always present may attain vertical ranges of 2 m or more during persistent wind episodes and must often be taken into account by ship captains when entering harbors with entrance channels of limited depth. Mortimer (1971) demonstrated that these

seiches rotate much like tidal waves; however, they are more complex in that several modes of oscillation can occur simultaneously. Lunar tides also occur in the Great Lakes, attaining up to 18 cm on Great Bay of Lake Michigan but only 3 cm on Lake Erie. Wind waves of the Great Lakes do not, of course, attain the huge dimensions of those in a North Pacific cyclone, but fall storms frequently generate waves in excess of 5 m in Lake Superior and 12-m waves have been reported. Great Lakes storms are particularly fearsome, however, both because of the suddenness with which they can develop and the steepness of the waves themselves. Coupled with subfreezing temperatures which cause instant freezing of freshwater spray on hulls and superstructure, the short steep waves and hurricane-like winds of an early winter cyclonic storm have sunk literally thousands of Great Lakes vessels, from early schooners and steamboats to modern 700-ft ore carriers like the Edmund Fitzgerald which was lost in Lake Superior during a November storm in 1977 (Ragotzkie 1983).

The thermal cycle in all these lakes is similar (Fig. 5), but with variations resulting from differences in latitude and depth. From November to late May the water in all lakes is nearly homothermous, although there may be a slight inverse stratification in mid-winter. In shallow, western Lake Erie winter homothermy often exists at less than 1.1°C and in Lake Superior homothermous winter temperatures of 1.7°C extend to at least 200 m but the deep-bottom water remains near 3.9°C. Thermal stratification occurs in all lakes, forming in early June in Lake Erie and in mid-July in Lake Superior. The depth of the epilimnion varies with each lake, although it is approximately 15 m in mid-summer in all except Lake Erie, where it may extend to 20 m. Stability of thermal stratification is generally low, in that both the temperature gradient and the actual temperatures are low (Chandler 1964).

Waters of these lakes are clear except in western Lake Erie. Secchi disc readings of 12 to 15 m are common in the open lakes, with decreasing values near shore. Transparency values in western Lake Erie are often less than 3 m, and less than 1 m in the estuaries.

As part of a global hydrological system, the Great Lakes continually receive moisture from air masses carried into the region by prevailing westerly winds. Correspondingly, the basin loses moisture in departing air masses and the outflow from the St. Lawrence River. On balance, the quantity of water lost approximately equals what is gained, but lake levels can vary substantially over short-term, seasonal and long-term periods.

Great Lakes water levels are regulated, but only in part. The outflow from Lake Superior has been controlled completely since the construction of a 16-gate dam across the outlet (St. Mary's River) in 1921. The only other regulated lake, Lake Ontario, has been controlled since the St. Lawrence Seaway was completed in 1958. The regulation of Lake Superior, including the Long Lac and Ogoki diversions, caused a slight increase (7.6) cm in Lake Erie water levels; the regulation has no effect on Lake Ontario. The Chicago diversion passes water out of Lake Michigan through the Illinois waterway and on to the Mississippi River. Flow through the Chicago diversion is limited by a U.S.

Figure 5. Circulation and stratification in the Great Lakes.

Supreme Court decree to 90 m³/s. The long-term effect of this diversion has been to lower the water level in Lake Erie by 4.3 cm. The diversion of water from Lake Erie to Lake Ontario through the Welland Canal has resulted in a lowering of 13.5 cm in Lake Erie levels and a consequently slight lowering of lakes Michigan-Huron levels. Since 1950, this diversion has averaged about 198 m³/s, currently 266 m³/s and is used for navigation and power generation. Also, a diversion of about 31 m³/s is made during the navigation season from the Niagara River at Tonawanda for use in the New York State Barge Canal. Other than these minor diversions, no regulation of Lake Erie water levels is presently possible. The net effect of all Great Lakes regulations and diversion has been to lower the level of Lake Erie by 10.2 cm.

NATURAL SETTING OF THE LAKE ERIE BASIN

Lake Erie Morphometry

Lake Erie is one of the largest freshwater lakes in the world, ranking 9th by area and 15th by volume. It is the southernmost of the North American Great Lakes, lying between 41°21'N and 42°50'N latitude and 78°50'W and 83°30'W longitude. The lake is narrow and relatively shallow for a lake of its size with its longitudinal axis oriented east-northeast (Fig. 4). Lake Erie is approximately 388 km long and 92 km wide, with a mean depth of 19 m and a maximum sounding of 64 m. The lake has a surface area of 25,657 km², a volume of 484 km³, a shoreline length of 1,402 km, and a surface elevation of 173.9 m above mean sea level. Based on bathymetry, Lake Erie can be naturally divided into three basins: western, central and eastern (Fig. 6).

Western Basin. The western basin, lying west of a line from the tip of Pelee Point, Ontario, to Cedar Point, Ohio, is the smallest and the shallowest with most of the bottom at depths between 7 and 10 m. In contrast with the other two basins, a number of bedrock islands and shoals are situated in the western basin and form a partial divide between it and the central basin. Topographically, the bottom is monotonously flat, except for the sharply rising islands and shoals in the central and eastern parts. The maximum depths in the basin are found in the interisland channels. The deepest sounding, 19 m, was made in a small depression north of Starve Island Reef; south of Gull Island Shoal, in another depression, a depth of 16 m has been recorded.

Central Basin. The central basin is divided from the western basin by the island chain and from the eastern basin by a relatively shallow sand and gravel bar (Fig. 7) between Erie, Pennsylvania and Long Point, Ontario. The central basin has an average depth of 18.5 m and a maximum depth of 26 m. Except for the rising slopes of a bar extending south-southeastward from Pelee Point, Ontario, the bottom of the central basin is extremely flat. This bar forms a depression in the bottom between it and the islands, known as the Sandusky sub-basin.

Figure 6. Bathymetric cross-section of the Lake Erie Basin.

Figure 7. Bottom sediments of Lake Erie.

Topographically, then, central Lake Erie can be divided into two parts; the Sandusky sub-basin and the much larger basin to the east. The roughly triangular Sandusky sub-basin covers an area of approximately 1350 km² or about 8.5% of central Lake Erie. On the west, the sub-basin is bounded by the islands on the east side by the Lorain-Vermilion sand and gravel deposit (Fig. 7), a ridge or bar crossing the lake between Lorain and the tip of Point Pelee. Over half the area of the sub-basin has depths greater than 12 m. Here the bottom is very flat; slopes of more than 0.5m/km are virtually non-existent. Silt and clay make up more than 95% of the bottom materials in the flat area. Water depths less than 12 m are found only on the shoreward rising slopes and on the Lorain-Vermilion sand and gravel deposit.

Eastern Basin. The eastern basin is relatively deep and bowl-shaped. Most of the basin's bottom lies below 25 m and the deepest sounding, 64 m, is found east-southeast of Long Point, Ontario. This basin is separated from the central basin by a glacially deposited bar which extends from the base of Long Point on the Ontario shore to Presque Isle at Erie, Pennsylvania. The bar contains a notch, known as the Pennsylvania channel, which reaches a depth of over 24 m and provides a subsurface connection for water circulation in both directions between the two basins.

Lake Erie Hydrology

Five natural hydrologic factors account for the net supply of water to estuaries and coastal wetlands: (1) precipitation, (2) runoff, (3) ground water, (4) evaporation and (5) intrusion of lake water. While the major source of water to Lake Erie is the upper Great Lakes via the Detroit River, several watersheds drained by 10 major streams and numerous small ones discharge into the western basin of Lake Erie. Each of these tributaries has a drowned mouth, creating estuarine conditions which have fostered the formation of coastal marshes.

More than 90% of the total inflow to Lake Erie comes from the Detroit River, the drainage outlet for the Upper Great Lakes. The average annual inflow at the head of the Detroit River is 5,140 m³/s, equivalent to 6.4 m of water covering Lake Erie. Surface runoff from the drainage area enters the lake via many smaller tributary rivers or by direct runoff from the shore area. Average annual runoff is estimated at 580 m³/s, outflow from Lake Erie is through the Niagara River at Buffalo and the Welland Canal diversion at Port Colborn. Combined outflow averages about 5,730 m³/s annually, equivalent to 7.1 m of water over Lake Erie.

Water depth in the lower Detroit River is influenced to a large extent by the water level of Lake Erie. Strong easterly winds can produce water levels in western Lake Erie which are 5 m above those in eastern Lake Erie. As a result, a partial reversal of flow in the Detroit River can be caused by water levels at its mouth being up to 1 m higher than at its head; under normal conditions there is typically a 1 m fall from Lake St. Clair to Lake Erie. Current velocities average 2.4 km/hr in the channels on both sides of Grosse Ile. Speeds are less in

shallows adjacent to the islands and channels, but at no place can the water be termed stagnant. The lowest flows of the Detroit River ordinarily occur in February (4,500 m³/s) and the highest in July or August (5,600 m³/s).

Two large rivers enter western Lake Erie and dominate water quality conditions in that basin. The Detroit River with a mean flow of 5,140 m³/s is the connecting channel for drainage from the upper Great Lakes and delivers 1.6 million tons of suspended solids and 33.6 million tons of dissolved solids to the lake each year. The Maumee River, at 137 m³/s is only 3% of the Detroit River flow but yields 2.3 million tons of suspended sediment and 1.4 million tons of dissolved material. This river drains 17,000 km² of primarily low lying farmland which accounts for its high sediment load. The high turbidity of the Maumee River significantly diminishes water clarity around the southern islands.

The waters of the western basin are more turbid than the other basins because of: (1) large sediment loads from the Detroit, Maumee, Portage and Sandusky rivers, (2) wave resuspension of silts and clay from the bottom, and (3) high algal productivity. Because the Detroit River accounts for most of the flow of water into Lake Erie it controls the circulation patterns in the western part of the basin. Its inflow penetrates far southward into the basin, retarding the dispersion of the sediment-laden Maumee River and the Michigan shore streams which results in high concentrations of contaminants along the western shore.

The Sandusky River is the largest stream flowing directly into the central basin. This river drains an area of 3,700 km², has an average flow rate of 30 m³/s, and discharges 270,000 tons of suspended sediment and 450,000 tons of dissolved solids to Sandusky Bay annually. Other major streams in the central basin include the Cuyahoga River, Grand River, Black River, and the Huron River with discharges of 23, 22, 11, and 9 m³/s respectively.

Although the central basin receives over 95% of its inflow from the western basin, the water is considerably less turbid and less biologically productive. Drainage from the western basin and inflow from the Sandusky River and other Ohio tributaries are concentrated in the Sandusky sub-basin and along the south shore where biological productivity and contaminants are the highest.

Water temperatures in the central and eastern basins are isothermal from fall to late spring; thermal stratification normally occurs below 15 m from June until September. In the central basin during the latter part of the stratified period the thin hypolimnion (cold, bottom water layer) may lose all of its dissolved oxygen (Fig. 5). The western basin typically freezes over each winter and the central and eastern basins occasionally freeze from shore to shore, except in the vicinity of isolated thermal discharges.

The storage capacity of Lake Erie is approximately 2.75 times the average annual inflow into it from tributary streams and the upper Great Lakes. Therefore, the theoretical retention of water entering the lake at the western end

flowing out the Niagara River is approximately 1,008 days. The shallow western basin of Lake Erie has a volume of 25 km³ and a water retention rate of about 53 days. The central basin's volume is 155 km³ and its retention rate is 322 days and the deeper eastern basin has a volume of 304 km³ and a retention rate of 635 days. The formation of a summer thermocline (Fig. 5) in the central and eastern basins causes these rates to be reduced in the epilimnion (warm, surface water layer).

The average annual rainfall in the Lake Erie basin is about 89 cm and ranges between 81 and 97 cm. The total land area which drains into Lake Erie, excluding that above the head of the Detroit River, is only about three times the area of the water surface of the lake. The large expanse of water affords a great opportunity for evaporation which has been estimated to be between 84 and 91 cm. This amount of evaporation is approximately equivalent to the average annual rainfall over the lake. During dry periods more water may be evaporated from the lake than flows into it from all of its tributaries. Under these conditions Lake Erie delivers into the Niagara River a smaller quantity of water than it receives from the Detroit River.

Lake Erie is noted for its severe storms, intense wave attack, and rapid water level changes. The high energy produced by these storms limits the existence of coastal wetlands to places where some type of natural or artificial protection is available. Correspondingly, the coastal marshes of western Lake Erie fall into three categories depending on the type of protection for the aquatic vegetation: (1) coastal lagoons behind barrier beaches, (2) estuarine tributary mouths, and (3) managed marshes protected by earthen and rip-rap dikes.

The record high water levels in Lake Erie during 1972-73 and again in 1985-86 contributed greatly to increased erosion and flooding of the shores. Because the narrow beaches fronting the coast were submerged, the shore bluffs were exposed to direct wave attack by storm waves and erosion by alongshore currents. Severe storms during these periods resulted in profound changes in shoreline configuration, disruption of coastal facilities, extensive property damage and loss of valuable coastal wetlands.

Water level changes on Lake Erie are of two principal types: (1) long-period fluctuations and (2) short-period fluctuations. Long-period fluctuations are related to volumetric changes of the lake, caused principally by variations in precipitation, evaporation, and runoff. These changes include both seasonal fluctuations and those occurring over a period of several years. Short-period fluctuations are due to a tilting of the lake surface by wind or by atmospheric pressure differentials. Wind tides, seiches, and harbor surges, which have periods from a few seconds to several days, are examples of short term fluctuations. Solar and lunar tides are negligible, resulting in maximum fluctuations of 3.3 cm.

Long-period water level fluctuations. The highest and lowest average monthly levels on Lake Erie generally occur in June and February, respectively. This seasonal variation typically ranges from 0.3 to 0.6 m. The

plane of reference for charts and navigational works on Lake Erie is known as Low Water Datum (LWD), and stands at an elevation of 173.3 m above the mean water level at Father Point, Quebec. The water level at Father Point, known as the International Great Lakes Datum or IGLD, 1955, approximates sea level at the place where the flow from the Great Lakes enters the ocean in the Gulf of St. Lawrence. The mean level of Lake Erie for the period of record (1900-86) is 173.8 m as measured by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. The highest average monthly level recorded was 174.9 reached in June 1986 and the lowest average monthly level recorded was 173.0 m in February 1936. This represents a range in lake elevation of nearly 2 m and a change in the lake's volume of approximately 10%.

Long-term variations in lake levels are the result of persistent low or high precipitation. In the mid-1960s the Great Lakes basin experienced low precipitation and correspondingly near-record low water levels in the lakes. In 1972-73, and again in 1985-86, precipitation was high and lake levels were extreme high. Records at Cleveland going back more than 100 years indicate no regular, predictable cycle of levels. The interval between periods of high and low water can vary widely.

Short-period water level fluctuations. Water levels at the ends of Lake Erie (Toledo and Buffalo) have a much greater fluctuation than near the center. Tilting of the lake surface is analogous to the up and down movement of the ends of a teeter-totter while the center is stable. High water levels coupled with northeast storms have produced a maximum rise in level of 3.1 m above Low Water Datum at Toledo. Conversely, low water and southwest winds have lowered the level to 2.4 m below Datum, a range of 5.5 m. Under the influence of wind, currents tend to bank up water on the windward shore. This forced movement of the lake surface is known as wind tide and the amount of rise produced is the wind setup. The resulting free oscillation of the lake surface caused by the inequality of water level is called a seiche. Such free oscillations are nearly continuous in the islands region and most often have a period of 12 hours and an amplitude of less than 0.7 m with a maximum amplitude of 2 m.

The major seiches on Lake Erie are essentially parallel to the longitudinal axis of the lake. Seiches along this axis have a period of approximately 12 to 14 hours. Seiche periods as recorded for 3 years at a water level gauge at Put-in-Bay on South Bass Island indicated that longitudinal seiches were occurring about 44% of the year. Surface winds from the southwest or northeast are likely to produce such seiches along the long axis of the lake. Wind records from Sandusky, Ohio are in agreement with the frequency of seiche periods; surface winds from these directions occur approximately 150 days or 41% of the year (Herdendorf and Braidech 1972).

LAKE ERIE ESTUARINE SYSTEMS

Delineation of Freshwater Estuaries

The Great Lakes are characterized by a wide variety of coastal features, including: bedrock cliffs, clay bluffs, sand beaches, marsh wetlands, and stream mouths. Tributaries enter the Great Lakes in three ways: (1) as free-flowing, single-channel streams at their mouths, (2) through deltaic distributary systems, or (3) at estuaries formed in the drowned mouths of the streams. To some degree estuaries are present on all of the Great Lakes but they are best developed in Lake Erie where crustal movements have extended them as far as 15 km upstream from the lake at the lower reaches of major rivers.

Great Lakes estuaries is a relatively new concept (Brant and Herdendorf 1972) and deserves some explanation. The arms of lakes that extend landward have evaded description and recognized distinction. For the most part such linear bodies of water have been referred to as river to within some indistinct proximity to the lake; whereas in reality these consist of a mixture of characteristics of these two water regimes. More recently, the *Glossary of Geology* (Bates and Jackson 1980) defined "freshwater estuaries" for the Great Lakes as "the lower reach of a tributary to the lake that has a drowned river mouth, shows a zone of transition from stream water to lake water, and is influenced by changes in lake level as a result of seiches or wind tides."

An estuary is usually defined as that part of the lower river course that is affected by the mixing of water from the stream with that from the receiving sea. Fairbridge (1968) considers an estuary to exist where the riverbed is "overdeepened" i.e., it lies below mean sea level and at least from time to time there is encroachment of seawater upstream. He goes on to explain that the single most important reason for the overdeepening is the postglacial rise of sea level.

The Great Lakes owe their origin to physiographic changes induced by Pleistocene glaciation. As the ice sheet paused in advances or retreats, ridges or moraines of glacial till were built up at their margins damming the natural drainage and forming glacial lakes. Lake Erie is the remnant of such a lake, which at its highest stage extended as far south as Fort Wayne, Indiana with its outlet to the southwest via the Wabash River. As the ice retreated, other outlets were uncovered and new lake stages were formed at successively lower levels. When the last glacier retreated from the bedrock sill at the head of the Niagara River, a new and final drainage outlet was made available. However, at that time the bedrock sill was as much as 30 m lower than at present because of the depression that had taken place under the weight of the glacial ice (Lewis et al. 1966).

Lake Erie tributaries, which developed as the high lake stages drained from the basin, were accelerated by base level lowering when the Niagara outlet was uncovered. Valleys were deeply cut into the glacial till at this time. With the

eventual rebound of the outlet and the subsequent rise in water level, the lake encroached up the valleys forming the present drowned river mouths or estuaries (Herdendorf 1987).

Schubel and Pritchard (1971) analyzed Pritchard's (1967) definition of an estuary in detail and after comparing it with ten other definitions, concluded that it most clearly described the phenomena:

"An estuary is a semi-enclosed coastal body of water which has a free connection with the open sea and within which sea water is measurably diluted with fresh water from land drainage."

According to this definition there are three characteristics which distinguish estuaries from other bodies of water: (1) an estuary is a coastal feature with some constriction at its opening to the sea; (2) an estuary has a free connection to the sea sufficient to allow continuous exchange of water between the ocean and the estuary and (3) an estuary is a place where there is a mixing of two kinds of water, river and sea.

These three basic concepts: (1) constriction, (2) continuous water exchange and (3) mixing of two kinds of water, can logically be applied to the Great Lakes. The foregoing discussion describes the existence of the first two situations in the Lake Erie system. Considerable evidence is also available to describe the mixing of two distinct water masses in zones, referred to as lake estuaries. Measurements of water quality and currents (Schroeder and Collier 1966, Brant and Herdendorf 1972) also demonstrate the encroachment of Great Lakes water into tributary mouths and the subsequent mixing of lake and river water in that area. This process is a necessary criteria for an estuary. For example, within the estuary of the Cuyahoga River, a nearly fourfold decrease in river mineralization was observed as it mixed with and was diluted by Lake Erie water. The extent of lake intrusion is affected by stream gradient, bathymetry, wind-tide, seiches and fluctuations in streamflow and lake level.

Comparison of Estuaries with Inland Wetlands

Estuaries and coastal wetlands differ in several ways from inland wetlands. The coast is subject to temporary, short-term water level changes. Seiches and storm surges affect the wetlands adjacent to shorelines of western Lake Erie and the lower Detroit River by raising or lowering the lake level as much as 2 m in a single day. Long-term cyclic water level changes, related to water budgets of the lake basins, also affect the coastal wetlands. Such fluctuations, occurring over a period of approximately 7 to 10 years, may cause vegetation dieback, erosion of the wetlands, or lateral displacement of the vegetative zones of wetlands. Many coastal wetlands, such as those along western Lake Erie, are exposed to relatively high wave energy. Such is not the case in the more quiescent inland wetlands.

Coastal wetlands along the Great Lakes do not appear to exhibit senescence, i.e., the aging process associated with inland freshwater wetlands. This process leads from open ponds to densely vegetated marshes, and eventually to dry fields. Because of the fluctuating water levels of the Great Lakes, constant rejuvenation of wetland communities occurs. As a consequence, diagrams in textbooks illustrating the gradual senescence of freshwater wetlands are more applicable to inland wetlands of the glaciated Midwest than to the Great Lakes coastal wetlands. Many inland freshwater wetlands undergo senescence and terrestrialization as a result of the formation of secondary and tertiary peat deposits. Peat is not common in coastal waters, but occurs in some lagoons. Coastal wetlands often display a diversity of landforms not normally encountered in other wetland environments. Owing to changes in the water levels of the Great Lakes since the retreat of the Pleistocene ice sheets, landforms such as barrier bars, deltas, beaches, spits, lagoons, and natural levees have been deposited or formed along the shoreline. Many of these geomorphic features promote the formation of wetlands, each with distinctive features, which results in the great variety and diversity of coastal wetlands found in the Great Lakes region.

Function and Value of Estuaries and Coastal Wetlands

Great Lakes estuaries and coastal wetlands are highly productive, diverse communities which interface between terrestrial and aquatic environments. The most obvious and unique feature of these wetlands is their characteristic vegetation, which provides a diverse community structure offering cover and food for the animal components of the system. Because of the ability of this vegetation to slow the flow rate of water passing through, wetlands are valuable for erosion control, trapping sediments before they reach the open lake, and attenuating the force of moderate waves to lessen their destructive power. However, intense lake storms can uproot macrophytes and eventually destroy wetlands. The same vegetation provides a natural pollution abatement mechanism by serving as a filter for coastal tributaries by reducing the quantity of nutrients and toxic pollutants being washed into the Great Lakes. Coastal wetlands are highly valued as recreational sites for activities such as hunting, trapping, fishing, boating access to larger bodies of water, birdwatching, and general aesthetic enjoyment. The combination of recreational desirability, agricultural and residential potential, and the proximity of estuaries and coastal wetlands to larger bodies of water have contributed to their status as endangered environments (Fig. 8). Their unique properties are susceptible to numerous natural and human-caused environmental disruptions that are now causing coastal wetlands to disappear at an alarming rate.

Estuaries of the Great lakes are multi-functional in nature because these environments are part of both the upland and the open-water ecosystems. It is the interface with the lakes that multiplies the wetland functions and contributes to their dynamics. In general, a multi-functioning wetland tends to have a higher value than those with narrower functions. However, coastal wetlands which are isolated by barriers or degraded by factors such as land drainage or high water may exhibit fewer functions and therefore have lower value. Coastal streams

Figure 8. Loss of coastal wetlands surrounding western Lake Erie 1800-1988.

and waterways enhance the interactions, whereas obstacles such as dikes result in coastal wetland fragmentation and loss of function. The effect of long-term lake level changes on the function of the coastal wetlands can also be significant. Function loss, then, can result from both upland-derived and lake-derived forces.

CULTURAL IMPACTS

The Great Lakes and the Lake Erie of today have been greatly modified from their natural condition, in terms of appearance of the coastline and of water quality. The Great Lakes were recognized by the first European settlers to the region as a natural concourse for colonization and trade (see Burns 1985). The region was also rich in natural resources, including timber, ores, furs, and fertile soils.

The growth of Ohio's population since the early 1800s (Fig. 9) exemplifies the population growth throughout the entire Great Lakes region and reflects the tremendous exploitation of the region's resources which has occurred over the past 200 years (see Burns 1985, and Rousmaniere 1979). The diversity of major cargoes handled at the eight Ohio ports on Lake Erie in 1986 and 1987 (Table 6) demonstrates the continued vital importance of the lake as a transportation route for ensuring the industrial and economic health of the basin.

The early development of commerce, particularly the availability of cheap raw materials for making steel, resulted in large concentrations of heavy industry and large metropolises, including Buffalo, Cleveland, and Toledo, on Lake Erie's shores. The lake was assumed by most to have an infinite capacity to receive wastes without adverse effect, and municipalities and industries discharged large amounts of a great variety of byproducts into its tributaries or directly into the lake itself. By the late 1950s and 1960s this practice had resulted in many noticeable changes in the appearance of the lake, such as discoloration by chemical effluents and the growth of algal mats which washed up on public beaches, as well as in the make-up of its biota, including the fish and invertebrates (Cap and Frederick 1981). Disposal of untreated human wastes into the lake caused health hazards due to bacteria and viruses, and most public beaches were closed. In industrialized areas persistent toxic and hazardous chemical wastes accumulated in the sediments of the lower reaches of rivers, in harbors, and in other areas near shore. Some flammable chemical wastes floated on the surface and made possible the infamous fires on the lower Cuyahoga River in Cleveland in the 1960s. Some localities were so severely polluted and so devoid of fish during that period that the popular press declared Lake Erie to be "dead." The magnitude of the pollution of Lake Erie has been described in detail in several books, including *Erie, the Lake that Survived* by Burns (1985), and *The Enduring Great Lakes*, edited by Rousmaniere (1979).

* 7th most populous state in 1985

Figure 9. Population growth in Ohio since 1800.

Table 6. Major cargoes handled at Ohio's eight Lake Erie ports, 1986-1987 (Ohio Dept. Transportation 1987).

Toledo	General cargo, coal, iron ore, bulk liquids, grains, petroleum, dry bulk, fertilizers, project cargoes
Sandusky	Coal, sand, limestone, gypsum ore, road salt, potash
Huron	Grain
Lorain	Taconite, sand, aggregates, millscale, limestone, potash, coal, coke
Cleveland	Steel, general cargo, dry bulk
Fairport Harbor	Limestone, ore, salt, sand, gravel
Ashtabula	Ores, stones, newsprints, coal, bulk cement, bulk & general cargo
Conneaut	Coal, coke, iron ore, limestone, coke breeze

Table 7. Some of the substances included on the International Joint Commission's 1986 "working list" of chemicals in the Great Lakes Basin.

PESTICIDES

Insecticides

Halogenated^a -- aldrin, chlordane, DDT (DDD, DDE), dieldrin, endosulfan, endrin, heptachlor, heptachlor epoxide, lindane and congeners, toxaphene

Organophosphorus/carbamate^b -- carbofuran, chlorpyrifos, diazinon, fonofos, malathion, terbufos

Herbicides

Triazines^b -- atrazine, cyanazine, metribuzin, simazine

Others^b -- 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, alachlor, linuron, metolachlor, trifluralin

OTHER ORGANICS^c

alkylated tins^b, benzene, chlorinated benzenes, chlorinated phenols, chlorinated PAHs, chlorinated toluenes^b, 1,2 dichloropropane, ethylbenzene, halogenated ethanes, halogenated ethylenes, halogenated methanes, isophorone, N-nitrosodiphenylamine, polychlorinated biphenyls, phenol, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), phthalate esters, 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin, toluene, xylenes^b

METALS^a

antimony, arsenic, beryllium, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, mercury, nickel, selenium, silver, thallium

^a Only those compounds on U.S. EPA list of 129 Priority Pollutants are shown.

^b None are U.S. EPA Priority Pollutants.

^c On U.S. EPA list of 129 Priority Pollutants unless footnoted

Federal (U.S and Canadian) as well as state and provincial legislation in the 1960s and 1970s, along with the Great Lakes Water Quality Agreements of 1972 and 1978, began the process of reducing or eliminating many pollutants to Lake Erie. Today the International Joint Commission (IJC) maintains a "Working List" of more than 350 pesticides, other organic compounds, and metals in the Great Lakes Basin, which include the 129 "priority pollutants" designated by the U.S. EPA (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987). Some of these are listed in Table 7. Eleven persistent, toxic chemicals or chemical groups which are widespread throughout the Great Lakes (Table 8) have been designated by the IJC as "critical pollutants" which need the most immediate remedial action.

Concurrent with the growth and impact of industry and commerce along the shores of Lake Erie, the watersheds draining into the lake were also tremendously modified. Trautman (1981) described the pristine forests and streams characteristic of the Lake Erie basin at the time of the first European explorations and early settlements:

Overwhelming evidence indicates that between 1750-1800 forests covered most of the Ohio Country, leaving the remainder in marshes, swamps, brush, 'bowling greens,' sandy beaches, and in wet, dry, tall grass, and wild plum prairies. . . Prior to 1800 the living and dead vegetation covering the Ohio Country was sufficient to prevent erosion of soil except in restricted areas along stream banks, beaches and steep hillsides. . . The streams were narrow and deep, they contained much brush and down timber but where shaded there was little aquatic vegetation. The waters were normally clear, containing little soil in suspension except during some freshets and floods. The bottoms of the waters were free of clayey silts, and were largely composed of sand, gravel, boulders, bedrock, and organic debris.

Most of this terrestrial forested ecosystem was radically transformed over the next 150 years, particularly in the southwestern drainage to the lake, to a man-managed agroecosystem which contains only relict farm woodlots and "green

Table 8. Substances in the Great Lakes designated as "critical pollutants" by the International Joint Commission (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987).

Total polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)
DDT and metabolites
Dieldrin
Toxaphene
2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (2,3,7,8-TCDD)
2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzofuran (2,3,7,8-TCDF)
Mirex
Mercury
Alkylated lead
Benzo(a)pyrene (B(a)P)
Hexachlorobenzene (BHC)

corridors" along streams. Of the period between 1851 and 1900 Trautman (1981) states: "Each year the amount of land increased which had been drained, ditched and/or tilled. . . Inorganic and organic pollutants increased greatly in number and amount. Clayey silt-bearing waters became conspicuous and widespread, and the silting over of stream and lake bottoms developed rapidly." Similar practices were prevalent as well in the western Canadian drainage of the lake.

The once-extensive system of marshes, swamps and wetlands which prior to 1850 covered an area of approximately 4,000 km² (1,540 sq. miles) between Vermilion, Ohio and the Detroit River and extended into Indiana along the Maumee River, was largely converted to highly-productive agricultural land during the next 100 years by draining, filling and diking. Today only about 150 km² of coastal marshes and wetlands remain (Herdendorf 1987).

Of the five Great Lakes basins, the Lake Erie basin presently has the smallest proportion of forested watershed (17%) and the highest proportions of agricultural (59%) and urban/industrial (9%) land-use (Table 9). The other four Great Lakes have at least 50% of their watersheds forested, no more than 32% in agriculture, and 4% or less in urban/industrial land-use. The most extensive agricultural land-use in the Great Lakes is in the southwestern drainage of Lake Erie (northwestern Ohio, northeastern Indiana and southeastern Michigan). In the northwestern Ohio watersheds in 1976, agriculture accounted for 77% of the land area, forests for only 8% (Baker 1988).

The intensive agriculture in the southwestern Lake Erie drainage has resulted in the export via tributaries of thousands of tons of sediment and its associated pollutants annually to Lake Erie's harbors, estuaries, and nearshore areas. Rural nonpoint source pollution (largely agricultural) is responsible for 51% of the total phosphorus delivered to the lake (Yaksich 1983). Rivers in the region also experience the highest residual concentrations of the herbicides used with corn and soybeans found anywhere in North America (Baker 1988). Phosphorus, as the limiting nutrient in Lake Erie, plays a major role in determining the amount of algae produced annually in the lake and ultimately the extent of anoxia (lack of oxygen) which develops each summer in the deeper waters of the central part of the lake. The U.S. and Canada have developed ongoing programs to reduce the export of phosphorus to the lake (Great Lakes Phosphorus Task Force 1985). Billions of dollars have been spent in both countries to reduce phosphorus inputs from point sources, such as municipal treatment plants, using such measures as phosphate detergent bans imposed by Michigan, Indiana, New York, Ontario, and in 1988, Ohio, and setting a maximum limit on phosphorus in waste treatment effluents of 1.0 mg/L. From all sources combined, the total amount of phosphorus entering Lake Erie on an annual basis is over twice the amount entering Lake Michigan and about three times the amount entering Lake Huron (Table 10), despite Lake Erie's much smaller water volume and shallower basin and thus its much more limited capacity to utilize the excessive phosphorus without deleterious effects.

Table 9. Land use in the Great Lakes Basin (Internat. Joint Commission 1980).

Lake	Forest	Agricultural	Urban/ Industrial	Other ^a
Erie	17	59	9	15
Superior	95	1	0.2	4
Huron	66	22	2	10
Michigan	50	23	4	23
Ontario	56	32	4	8

^a Scrub, brush, wetland

Table 10. Estimated total phosphorus load (metric tons) to lakes Michigan, Huron, and Erie, 1975-1982 (Lesht and Rockwell 1987).

Year	Michigan ^a	Huron ^a	Erie ^a	Erie ^b
1975	7,049	3,641	12,722	18,246
1976	6,656	4,145	14,336	18,668
1977	4,666	3,106	13,496	19,312
1978	6,245	4,598	18,351	13,312
1979	7,659	4,224	10,861	12,530
1980	6,574	4,650	13,775	9,863
1981	4,091	2,824	9,372	--
1982	4,084	4,032	11,269	--

^a Data from International Joint Commission

^b Data from Yaksich et al. (1982)

Measures aimed at point sources of phosphorus have been successful in reducing the total loading of phosphorus to the lake; however, nonpoint source (mostly agricultural) controls have been much harder to legislate and to implement. Most of the effort in the nonpoint source arena has involved the sponsoring of conservation tillage demonstration projects within the Lake Erie basin, both in the U.S. and Ontario, with the purpose of documenting the effectiveness of reduced tillage methods in slowing soil erosion and phosphorus loss while maintaining profitability for the farmer (Honey Creek Joint Bd. Supervisors 1982, National Assoc. Conserv. Districts 1985). Most aspects of the demonstration programs have been successful, yet farmers and landowners on the whole have been slower to adopt conservation tillage and other "best management practices" (e.g., stream bank erosion control, and livestock waste management) than desirable to measurably reduce phosphorus loading to the lake.

Unquestionably, the extensive urban and industrial development of the Lake Erie shore and the land-use changes in its drainage basin over the past 200 years have resulted in major environmental problems for the biota of the lake (see the papers in this volume by Johnson, Klarer, Monaco and Lorenz, and Stuckey) as well as for the millions of people who rely on the lake for drinking water, fish, recreation and industrial uses. Of 50 pollution issues presented for prioritization to representatives of the coastal zone management offices and National Sea Grant College Program institutions in the Great Lakes states (Harvey and Zacherle 1984), the following issues were ranked as the ten most important (in order of decreasing importance): (1) Effects of synthetic organic chemicals on the marine environment, (2) effects of ocean dumping of sewage sludge (probably in reference to open lake dumping of dredge spoils), (3) deterioration of the Great Lakes as a drinking water source, (4) cumulative effects of man-induced changes on selected coastal areas and estuaries, (5) adequacy of baseline information, (6) effects of agricultural nonpoint source contamination in estuaries and coastal areas, (7) long-term effects of PAHs and their metabolites in the marine environment, (8) effects of nutrient loading on estuaries, coastal zones and the Great Lakes, (9) effects of pipeline discharge of industrial waste, (10) effects of urban and suburban nonpoint source contamination in estuaries and coastal areas.

The International Joint Commission has identified several emerging issues for the Great Lakes:

- New persistent toxic substances, which will be introduced to the Great Lakes ecosystem in increasing quantities, "with production capacity and consumptive demand greatly exceeding government capacity for regulation and enforcement."

- Biotechnology, which holds the potential for solving pollution problems, such as creation of wetlands for waste treatment, and new technologies for toxic waste disposal and recovery. Genetically engineered bacteria could be developed for improving the performance of water and sewage treatment plants, as well as for modifying, enhancing and manipulating species "to

sustain continued high levels of resource productivity," and for reducing the dependence of agriculture on chemical pesticides.

- Waste management, including the handling and disposal of wastes from agriculture, mining, industry and municipalities; as well as the threat to groundwater and surface water by leachate from both inactive and currently operating dumpsites.
- Deficiency of present institutional arrangements to respond adequately to either the increasing complexity of emerging Great Lakes issues or their consequences.
- Enforcement and surveillance to prevent unregulated discharges and to provide compliance monitoring. "While public concerns and expectations for the environment will result in increased legislative and regulatory responses, the ability to implement the approaches and achieve the desired goals will continue to be severely constrained by a lack of human and financial resource commitments."
- Allocation and beneficial uses of Great Lakes resources in the presence of competing and conflicting demands.
- A growing policy role for corporations in achieving the Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement objectives. "A major challenge for industry over the near term will be the extent to which innovation and clean technology is applied to production activities. . . Governments cannot implement the Agreement alone and, therefore, it will be essential that this emerging trend of corporate assistance be encouraged and supported to bring additional expertise and resources to bear on water quality problems in the Great Lakes."
- Heightened public concerns over the state of the Great Lakes ecosystem, and heightened public expectations of both industry and governments to remedy the pollution problems in the Great Lakes (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987).

In order to launch a concerted and effective effort toward improving the water and sediment quality in the most severely impacted areas of the Great Lakes, the International Joint Commission has established 42 "Areas of Concern" (AOCs) in the Great Lakes and their connecting channels. Those along Lake Erie (Fig. 10) include the Detroit River and the lower 2.6 miles of the River Raisin in Michigan; the lower parts of the Maumee, Black, Cuyahoga and Ashtabula rivers and their harbors in Ohio, the Buffalo River in New York, and Wheatley Harbour in Ontario. The pollutants in these AOCs have come from rural and urban nonpoint sources, industrial and municipal point sources, combined sewer overflows and waste disposal sites. Present-day major sources of contamination include "in-place pollutants" which are trapped in or slowly released from sediments in the AOCs. Table 11 lists the major types of problems in the Lake Erie AOCs (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985). All of the problems probably exist to some extent in each AOC.

Figure 10. Areas of Concern in the Great Lakes Basin (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987).

A coordinated and formalized effort to improve each of the 42 AOCs is being developed by means of a Remedial Action Plan (RAP). These plans are drawn up by RAP committees comprised of members from local, regional and state or provincial governments, from industries, environmental organizations, and the public at large. Of the Lake Erie AOCs as of early 1988, the only RAP that had been submitted to the IJC's Water Quality Board for review and potential future implementation was that for the River Raisin. That river, which enters the lake at Monroe in the southeastern corner of Michigan, contains high concentrations of PCBs in sediments, water and fish. Consequently, a state fish consumption advisory is in effect for that AOC. The state department of natural resources has included several landfills, waste lagoons and industrial sites within the AOC on a priority cleanup list. The proposed RAP will compile existing data for use in

developing a plan to restore fishing in the AOC; it will determine data deficiencies and recommend new investigations to help define the problems and sources; and further, it will recommend appropriate remedial actions (Great Lakes Reporter 1988).

Some parts of the Lake Erie ecosystem have shown improvement since the early 1970s, when many of the programs to reduce or eliminate pollution from point sources were first initiated. The apparent quality of the lake's water has greatly improved, as judged by the reduced presence of the summer algal mats and the reopening of beaches all along the lakeshore. The high productivity of recreational fish species such as yellow perch and walleye in the western basin, and less so in the central basin, have led to the claim that Lake Erie is the "walleye capitol of the world." In 1982 recreational boating and fishing together comprised an approximately \$19 million annual industry in the central basin, and the value of private-boat and charter sportfishing in the western basin alone in 1981 was \$155 million (Hushack et al. 1985). While localized severe pollution remains, particularly in the Areas of Concern, the open lake and many nearshore regions are showing sign of improvement, as measured by reduced fecal bacterial counts and a trend toward lower mean annual phosphorus and chlorophyll *a* concentrations in the open lake. The complexity of the recovery

Table 11. Major types of pollutants in the Lake Erie Areas of Concern (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985).

Type	Area of Concern
Conventional Pollutants	All
Heavy Metals	All
Toxic Organics	All
Contaminated Sediments	All
Impacted Biota	All except Wheatley Harbour
Fish Consumption Advisories	All except Maumee R. and Cuyahoga R.
Aesthetics	All except Ashtabula R., Buffalo R., and Wheatley Harbour
Eutrophication	Maumee R., Wheatley Harbour, Detroit R.
Beach Closings	Detroit R.

process is pointed out, however, by the less encouraging response of other important indicators, including an apparently increasing or stabilized oxygen depletion rate in the central basin hypolimnion and a steadily increasing open-lake nitrate+nitrite concentration (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987). In the presence of modern civilization, Lake Erie cannot be returned to its pristine condition; to return it to an acceptable quality will require a long-continuing major investment of funds and human resources committed to scientific investigation, technological advancement and concerted management.

REFERENCES

- Baker, D.B. 1988. Sediment, nutrient and pesticide transport in selected lower Great Lakes tributaries. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Chicago, Illinois. EPA 905/4-88-001. 117 pp. + app.
- Bates, R.L. and J. C. Jackson. 1980. Glossary of Geology, 2nd ed. Am. Geol. Inst., Falls Church, VA. 749 pp.
- Brant, R. A. and C. E. Herdendorf. 1972. Delineation of Great Lakes estuaries. Proc. 15th Conf. Great Lakes Research, Internat. Assoc. Great Lakes Research 15: 710-718.
- Burns, N.M. 1985. Erie, the lake that survived. Rowman & Allanheld Publ., Totowa, New Jersey. 320 pp.
- Cap, R.K., and V.R. Frederick, Jr. (eds.) 1981. Proceedings of the conference on changes in the biota of lakes Erie and Ontario. Bull. Buffalo Soc. Nat. Sci. 25(4): 1-120.
- Chandler, D. C. 1964. The St. Lawrence Great Lakes. Verh. Internat. Verein. Limnol. 15: 59-75.
- Fairbridge, R. W. 1968. Encyclopedia of geomorphology. Reinhold Book Corp., New York. 1295 pp.
- Great Lakes Phosphorus Task Force. 1985. United States task force plan for phosphorus load reductions from non-point, and point sources on Lake Erie, Lake Ontario, and Saginaw Bay. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Great Lakes National Program Office, Chicago, Illinois.
- Great Lakes Reporter. 1988. Great Lakes Areas of Concern update. 5(1): 5-8.
- Great Lakes Water Quality Board. 1985. 1985 report on Great Lakes water quality. Internat. Joint Commission, Windsor, Ontario. 212 pp.

- Great Lakes Water Quality Board. 1987. 1987 report on Great Lakes water quality. Internat. Joint Commission, Windsor, Ontario. 236 pp.
- Harvey, S.E., and A.W. Zacherle. 1984. National marine pollution issues--state and regional perspectives. Virginia Sea Grant College Program. VSGCP-R-84-011 C3.
- Herdendorf, C. E. 1982. Large lakes of the world. *J. Great Lakes Research* 8(3): 379-442.
- Herdendorf, C.E. 1984. Lake Erie water quality 1970-1982: a management assessment. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Great Lakes National Program Office, Chicago, Illinois. EPA-905/4-84-007. 144 pp.
- Herdendorf, C.E. 1987. The ecology of the coastal marshes of western Lake Erie: a community profile. U.S. Fish Wildl. Serv. Biol. Rep. 85(7.9). 171 pp. + microfiche app.
- Herdendorf, C. E. and L. L. Braidech. 1972. Physical characteristics of the reef area of western Lake Erie. Ohio Dept. Nat. Res., Div. Geol. Survey Rep. Invest. 82. 90 pp.
- Herdendorf, C. E., S. M. Hartley, and M. D. Barnes. 1981. Fish and wildlife resources of the Great Lakes coastal wetlands. Vol.1: Overview. U. S. Fish and Wildl. Serv. FWS/OBS-81/02-V1. 469 pp.
- Honey Creek Joint Bd. Supervisors. 1982. Honey Creek watershed project, final program evaluation report, 1979-1981. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. 57 pp.
- Hutchinson, G. E. 1957. A treatise on limnology -- volume 1, geography, physics and chemistry. John Wiley & Sons, New York. 1015 pp.
- Hushak, L.J., T.L. Napier, and C.S. Thraen. 1985. Economic and policy factors which affect participation in water-based recreation on Ohio's Lake Erie. pp. 23-36. *In*: Ohio Sea Grant Program proposal 1985-1986, Vol. 2. Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio.
- Internat. Joint Commission. 1980. Pollution in the Great Lakes Basin from land use activities. Windsor, Ontario. 141 pp.
- Jude, D. J., F. J. Tesar, T. J. Tomlinson, T. J. Miller, N. J. Thurber, G. G. Godum, and J. A. Door. 1979. Inshore Lake Michigan fish populations near the Donald C. Cook Nuclear Power Plant during preoperational year 1973, 1974. Univ. Michigan, Great Lakes Research Div. Spec. Rep. No. 71. 529 pp.

- Lesht, B.M., and D.C. Rockwell. 1987. The state of the middle Great Lakes: results of the 1984 water quality survey of lakes Erie, Huron, and Michigan. Argonne National Laboratory, Argonne, Illinois. ANL/ER-87-1. 141 pp.
- Lewis, C. F. M., T. W. Anderson, and A. A. Berti. 1966. Geological and palynological studies of early Lake Erie deposits. Proc. 9th Conf. Great Lakes Research, Great lakes Res. Div., Univ. Michigan. 9: 176-191.
- Mortimer, C. H. 1971. Large-scale oscillatory motions and seasonal temperature changes in Lake Michigan and Lake Ontario. Spec. Rep. No. 12. Center for Great Lakes Studies, Univ. Wisconsin, Milwaukee.
- National Assoc. Conserv. Districts. 1985. Lake Erie conservation tillage demonstration projects: evaluating management of pesticides, fertilizer, residue to improve water quality. Fort Wayne, Indiana. 22 pp.
- Ohio Department of Transportation. 1987. Ohio's Lake Erie ports and Ohio River terminals 1986-1987. Ohio Dept. Transportation, Div. Water Transportation, Columbus, Ohio. 100 pp.
- Ragotzkie, R. A. 1983. The Great Lakes: a microcosm of the world ocean. pp. 159-173 *In: Man and the marine environment.* CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida.
- Rawson, D. S. 1939. Some physical and chemical factors in the metabolism of lakes. Amer. Assoc. Advancement Sci. Publ. No. 10. pp. 9-26.
- Rawson, D. S. 1955. Morphometry as a dominant factor in the productivity of large lakes. Verh. Internat. Verein. Limnol. 12: 164-175.
- Rousmaniere, J. (ed.) 1979. The enduring Great Lakes. W.W. Norton & Co., New York. 112 pp.
- Schroeder, M. E. and C. R. Collier. 1966. Water-quality variations in the Cuyahoga River at Cleveland, Ohio. U. S. Geol. Survey Prof. Paper No. 550-C: 251-255.
- Schubel, J. R. and D. W. Pritchard. 1971. What is an estuary? pp. 1-11 *In: Estuarine environment.* Amer. Geol. Inst., Washington D. C.
- Trautman, M.B. 1981. The fishes of Ohio. 2nd ed. Ohio State Univ. Press, Columbus, Ohio. 782 pp.
- Wetzel, R. G. 1983. Limnology, 2nd ed., Saunders College Publ., Philadelphia. 767 pp.
- Yaksich, S.M. 1983. Summary report of the Lake Erie Wastewater Management Study. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. 31 pp.

Yaksich, S.M., D.A. Melfi, D.B. Baker, and J.W. Kramer. 1982. Lake Erie nutrient loads, 1970-1980. Tech. Rept., Lake Erie Wastewater Management Study, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. 194 pp.